

Introducing Open Government Data Ecosystems: Opportunities and Challenges

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As our societies advance through what is known as the fourth industrial revolution, the amount of published open government data has escalated over the past few decades, as it is considered a critical driver of competitiveness and a catalyst for solving social and sustainability challenges. Combining different sectors and perspectives, the project 'Towards a sustainable Open Data ECOSystem' (ODECO) aims to address the central challenges of realizing a user-driven, circular, inclusive, open data ecosystem. Understanding open government data from an ecosystem perspective can help to identify opportunities and challenges to unleash its potential. We invite interested parties to take part in the project.

Scholars define open government data as any “non-privacy-restricted and non-confidential data produced with public money and made available without any restrictions on its usage or distribution.” Different theories and models have been applied to analyze the data processes to understand how to achieve the open government data promises, such as the data lifecycle, supply chain, or value chain. However, it has been recognized that these models fail to cope with the complexity of the emerging interactions and provide a limited understanding of the needs and the context of open data use. From a socio-technical system perspective, theorists assert that information system problems and failures result from overemphasizing technical expertise and underappreciating social factors.

The attention to the feedback and the interrelationships become essential topics to explore, especially when considering that the benefits of open data are expected to come primarily from external innovative data use. In the current approaches, however, most open data initiatives are mainly driven by the *suppliers* of data rather than considering the wide range of factors involved and users' perspectives. In contrast, experts agree that achieving the full potential of open data requires coordination and collaboration beyond government efforts. To fully understand and appreciate open government data implementation complexity, it is necessary to consider the needs and abilities of all the actors involved, the characteristics of the resources available, and the relationships between all the elements involved. This requires a more comprehensive approach to planning and designing open data initiatives, and that the ecosystem perspective seeks to fulfil.

Untangling Open Government Data Complexity through an Ecosystem Approach

The concept of an *ecosystem* was initially introduced in ecology by the British ecologist Arthur Tansley in 1935. Tansley recognized the interconnectedness of living and non-living elements within a natural system, where various factors interact with their physical environment through cycles. The dynamic and coevolving nature of these interactions highlight the functioning as a "whole" of an ecosystem within a given area. This perspective has been applied to other fields beyond ecology, including theories within business, information science, innovation, digitalization, and open government, emphasising the importance of understanding the larger context in which different actors operate.

Ecosystem-related theories recognize the self-organising and autonomous functionality of elements within a system, where connections are established through feedback loops and local specialisation rather than top-down definitions. Collaborative arrangements are necessary to create value in these systems. Open data can be considered an ecosystem that relies on both technical and

social interdependence, requiring a cohesive integration of its elements to facilitate the functioning of diverse tools for open data provision and use.

Open Government Data Ecosystem

Figure 1. Adapted from Pollock, R. (2011). "Building the (Open) Data Ecosystem – Open Knowledge Foundation Blog." This figure illustrates the cyclical process an Open Government Data Ecosystem should have to work effectively. The original image was modified to highlight the relevance of considering contextual aspects such as governmental actors in the case of Open Government Data and the Legal Frameworks

Understanding open government data from an ecosystem perspective can help identify opportunities and challenges, such as offering solutions for open data availability through shared metadata tracking frameworks that allow for consistent management of large and diverse data sets. Studies have shown that active intervention by governments is required to address feedback mechanisms, sustainability, and links between data supply and demand, as well as interactions among stakeholders. Cultivating ecosystems around government practices and interactions with constituents can help achieve values associated with open governance. Constraints on the publication and use of open government data include government and user capabilities, practices, policies, and interactions and relationships among government, data resources, users, citizens, and other stakeholders.

Open Government Data Ecosystems and the Challenges ahead

To fully reap the benefits of open data ecosystems, governments and other actors must address various challenges related to policy, technology, financing, organisation, culture, legal frameworks, and ICT infrastructures. Rufus Pollock (2011), who founded the Open Knowledge Foundation, suggests three main changes that must be addressed to develop an open data ecosystem: infomediaries need to publish what they produce, better ways to publish and share data are required; and publishers must

notify users of patches with automated integration of tools. Meanwhile, researchers from the open data field have found that there are several key elements that an open data ecosystem should have to create value:

- Releasing and publishing open data on the internet.
- Searching and evaluating data and licences.
- Analysing and visualising data.
- Interpreting and discussing data.
- Locating user pathways with directions on how to use data.
- Quality management systems.
- Different types of metadata to link open data.

In more recent efforts, researchers from a variety of fields, such as spatial information sciences, policy management, social design, digital government, computer sciences, law, and education, have been working to identify the primary needs that an open data ecosystem must meet to create value and be sustainable. According to a study published in 2022, an open data ecosystem must be user-driven, circular, inclusive, and skill-based. That involves strategies for matching the demand and supply of open data, investigating relationships between different types of open data, ensuring participation and co-creation by problem owners, and equipping users with the skills needed to realise the potential of open data.

In connection to this research, as one of the first dedicated efforts to achieve the full potential of open data the 4-year project funded by the European Commission “Towards a sustainable Open Dada Ecosystem” (ODECO) seeks to address current and future challenges in creating a user-driven, circular, inclusive data ecosystem. The project is a training network initiative consisting of 15 individual projects led by PhD students - two of which are situated at the Copenhagen Campus of Aalborg University. If you want to learn more about these efforts, we invite you to visit the project website (<https://odeco-research.eu/>) or contact the researchers involved. On a municipal level, the project “Maximising the availability and use of local Open Government Data” focuses on engaging municipal officers across Denmark to develop the research. If you may be willing to participate, please contact the lead researcher María Elena López Reyes (melr@ikp.aau.dk).

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